

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Guide on the diversity of OS contributions, roles and activities

Actionable
version

Definition

This guide highlights the diversity of open science (OS) contributions, roles, and activities that should be recognised in research assessment and career evaluation. It emphasises that scholarly contributions extend beyond publications and citations, encompassing data sharing, software, citizen science, mentoring, infrastructure support, and stakeholder engagement. The goal is to support responsible research assessment (RRA) by valuing contributions that make research more transparent, inclusive, equitable, and societally relevant.

Relevant SCOPE stages

This guide is most relevant in SCOPE phases:

- Options for evaluating: Identifying diverse OS contributions and roles to include in assessment.
- Probe deeply: Critically reviewing how these contributions are acknowledged and ensuring fairness across disciplines and roles.

When and how to use

Use this guide when:

- Designing assessment protocols for recruitment, promotion, or funding that go beyond publications.
- Implementing narrative CVs that allow researchers to showcase OS practices.
- Recognising team science and collaboration, where not all contributions are reflected in authorship.
- Engaging stakeholders (policy-makers, practitioners, citizen scientists) in assessment frameworks.

How to use:

- Map contributions broadly → Include activities such as data curation, software development, mentoring, open peer review, and citizen science.
- Consider multiple stakeholders → Acknowledge contributions from librarians, data stewards, infrastructure staff, and other enablers of OS.
- Integrate OS into skills frameworks → Ensure assessments value skills in data management, openness, collaboration, and public engagement.
- Adapt to context → Weight contributions differently depending on discipline, career stage, and role.

Guidance

- Shift from narrow metrics: Avoid evaluating researchers only through publications and citations; include diverse OS outputs and activities.
- Recognise invisible contributions: Value contributions that enable OS also from non-academic staff.
- Apply CRediT taxonomy → Use the Contributor Role Taxonomy (14 roles, e.g. conceptualization, data curation, software, supervision) to capture diverse contributions.
- Encourage inclusivity and equity: Consider contributions to citizen science, public engagement, and collaboration with underrepresented communities.
- Support systemic change: Align assessment systems with UNESCO OS principles (transparency, inclusiveness, equity, sustainability).
- Use open infrastructures and tools: Examples include EOSC (European Open Science Cloud), OpenEdition, HAL, Episciences, Jisc Open Policy Finder.
- Value OS skills: Ensure training, recognition, and reward systems encourage data sharing, collaboration, and engagement.
- Foster cultural change: Organisations that have signed the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) should integrate OS contributions explicitly into their assessment practices.

Further reading

GrasPOS SCOPE+I Resources

- Guide on promoting OS contributions in a narrative CV
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525987>

Other

- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>
- CRediT Contributor Role Taxonomy (ANSI/NISO, 2022): <https://credit.niso.org/>
- Open Science Skills Visualisation (McCaffrey et al., 2020):
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4727592>

